

Local Government in Germany

Responses to Urban-Rural Challenges

edited by

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The H2020-MSCA-RISE-2018 project aims to provide solutions for local governments that address the fundamental challenges resulting from urbanisation. To address these complex issues, 18 partners from 17 countries and six continents share their expertise and knowledge in the realms of public law, political science, and public administration. LoGov identifies, evaluates, compares, and shares innovative practices that cope with the impact of changing urban-rural relations in major local government areas (WP 1-5).

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Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments

5.1. Intergovernmental Relations of Local Governments in Germany: An Introduction

Nicole Lieb, *Ludwig Maximilian University of Munich*

System of Local Tasks and State Supervision

The structural distinction between the two poles of self-government tasks (tasks of a local government's own sphere of influence; *Selbstverwaltungsaufgaben*) and state tasks (tasks in the assigned sphere of influence or external tasks; *staatliche Auftragsangelegenheiten*) is elementary for the understanding of intergovernmental relations of local government in Germany. Due to the existence of different task categories¹²⁴ in horizontal and vertical respects, voluntary or compulsory, but also thematically and structurally, as well as the fragmentation of *Länder* law, it is not easy to filter out a general system of intergovernmental relations. In the course of development, a distinction has been made in Germany between *Länder* with a dualistic task model (e.g. Bavaria) and *Länder* with a monistic (uniform) task model (e.g. Brandenburg).¹²⁵ In the relationship between the county and the respective *Land*, the tasks are carried out in the same structures as in the relationship between the municipality and the *Land*, i.e. separately depending on whether the dualistic or the monistic system is the basis. As a result, the same types of tasks are to be distinguished at the county level as at the municipal level. The debate on the various task categories and the resulting legal consequences must take place according to the affiliation to one of the two models. In *Ländern* with the dualistic system, local governments can be assigned state tasks as external tasks, which are generally outside the scope of Article 28(2) of the Basic Law (BL). Their imposition is an intervention that needs to be justified and often leads to intergovernmental disputes, particularly because of the financial implications of resolving them. That is why local governments are increasingly defending themselves against the excessive burden of tasks (*Aufgabenüberbürdung*). This applies mostly to RLGs which are already struggling with their financial capacity and don't get enough support from the higher local levels.

Intergovernmental relations are also relevant when a municipality wants to defend itself against a measure of state supervision. In the event of a dispute, it is usually a question of the

¹²⁴ Around the two poles there are further categories such as 'compulsory task according to instructions' (*Pflichtaufgabe nach Weisung*), 'compulsory task without instructions' (*Pflichtaufgabe ohne Weisung*), 'lending of organs' (*Organleihe*), 'actions being taken as lower state administrative authorities' (*Tätigwerden als untere staatliche Verwaltungsbehörde*), etc. In all cases there is an interlocking with the state administrative organization through the so-called state supervision of the local governments.

¹²⁵ A further detailed explanation of the two systems can be found at Martin Burgi, *Kommunalrecht* (6th edn, CH Beck 2019) para 8.

competence of the state authority and the scope of its supervisory powers.¹²⁶ The result depends – as already mentioned above – on whether the municipality is involved in the execution of a self-government task or a state task. State supervision can be divided into two dimensions: on the one hand, it serves the municipalities as a defensive right, while at the same time it can also be used as a controlling tool. It is governed by the *Länder* constitutions and, depending on its scope, is intended to ensure legality (legal supervision; *Rechtsaufsicht*) or coordination within the state as a whole (subject-specific supervision; *Fachaufsicht*). Legal supervision aims to ensure compliance with formal and substantive European law, federal and *Länder* law. It is open to the execution of voluntary and compulsory tasks without instructions. In the case of state tasks or compulsory tasks in accordance with instructions, the standard of expediency is added to the standard of legality. In principle, authority to issue directives (*Weisungsbefugnisse*) only exists for the last-mentioned tasks. The instruments are to be differentiated according to preventive or repressive supervision. The following supervisory instruments are provided for in all *Länder*: right to information (*Informationsrecht*), right of objection or cancellation (*Beanstandungs- bzw. Aufhebungsrecht*), right to order or instruction (*Anordnungs- bzw. Anweisungsrecht*) and substitute performance (*Ersatzvornahme*). The selection within the supervisory instruments should be based on the prohibition of excessive use, i.e. graduated according to the intensity of the intervention. State supervision gains the greatest relevance in the course of monitoring the budgetary system of the municipalities. The respective Municipal Code contains the principle of balanced budgets. If this rule is violated by the municipality, the state supervisory authority is obliged to ensure that the municipality restores the budget balance. In the relationship between the county and the respective *Land*, the tasks are carried out in the same structures as in the relationship between the municipality and the *Land*, i.e. separately according to whether the dualistic or monastic system is the basis. As with the municipalities, but to a much greater extent, there is also an interlocking with the administrative organization of the *Land* at the lower level. The scope of tasks of the counties is, of course, to be delimited not only with respect to the *Land* but also with respect to the municipalities belonging to the county. There are no significant differences between urban and rural areas with regard to intergovernmental relations, only with regard to which authority is specifically responsible for supervision.

The legal protection against a supervisory action is available to a local government and takes place before the Administrative Court (*Verwaltungsgericht*). Its decision depends on whether it is involved in the handling of a self-government task or a state task. In most cases, it is a question of the delimitation of the competence of a state authority and the scope of its supervisory powers. As mentioned earlier, the right of local self-government in Article 28(2) BL gives local governments a strong position to defend themselves.

¹²⁶ For legal protection in the relationship between the state and the municipality, see Burgi, *Kommunalrecht*, above, para 9.

Local Authority Associations

Not municipalities, but representatives of municipal interests organized under private law are the Local Authority Associations (*Kommunale Spitzenverbände*), which are very powerful in political life: The German Association of Cities and Municipalities (*Deutscher Städte- und Gemeindebund*), in which mainly small and medium-sized municipalities and cities (approx. 13,000) are grouped together, the German Association of Cities (*Deutscher Städtetag*), an association of larger towns and cities (approx. 3,600), and the German Association of Counties (*Deutscher Landkreistag*; approx. 295), each with state associations. They are voluntary associations on a private law basis so they don't underlie state supervision. These umbrella organizations represent the interests of the counties, cities and municipalities vis-à-vis other political actors and exert a decisive influence on the *Länder* and federal governments. An indication of the increased importance of European law in this area as well is the existence of the so-called European Office of German Local Self-Government in Brussels.

The coordination of their work lies within the Federal Association of Local Authority Associations (founded on 19 May 1953). The Local Authority Associations are organized at both federal and state level while they are financed primarily by membership fees or by levies and are thus independent and autonomous in relation to state directives. This enables them to represent the interests of their members decisively. Despite numerous advances, the Local Authority Associations have so far not succeeded in establishing a qualified right to be heard or even a right of legislative co-determination by supplementing Article 28 of the Basic Law. However, individual *Länder* (such as Bavaria, Baden-Württemberg, Hesse, Saxony, Thuringia and Brandenburg) guarantee constitutionally that they can participate in legislative procedures. Other external functions include an advisory and consultation function for planning projects and decisions of the federal government and the *Länder* relevant to local authorities, and the representation of the interests of the members of the associations vis-à-vis the federal government and the *Länder*. Another major field of activity of the Local Authority Associations is their internal functions, e.g. the organization of the exchange of experience and opinion-forming process between the members, as well as their technical and legal advice.

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